

Tectonics

Supporting Information for

Provenance of the Mesozoic succession of Franz Josef Land (north-eastern Barents Sea): Paleogeographic and tectonic implications for the High Arctic

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Attachment 2. Stratigraphic column and photo of Location 3 and 4

**Location 3
Berghaus Island**

**Location 4
Graham Bell Island**

- coarse- to medium grained sands and sandstones
- fine-grained sands and sandstones
- clay, argillites
- siltstones
- matrix supported conglomerates
- pebbles and cobbles
- coals
- dated samples